

THE MANAGEMENT OF CALCANEUM SPUR (VATAKANTAKA) BY AGNIKARMA THERAPY: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Vatakantaka (Calcaneal spur) is common source of heel pain causes excruciating type of pain in the heel and disability. *Vatakantaka* is one of the *vatavyadhi*. During walking or running on uneven road if the foot landed improperly, the *vata* ceases in *gulf sandhi* produces as if prick by the thorn hence it termed as a *Vatakantaka*. Calcaneus is the heel bone. When it is met with constant pressure, calcium deposition occurs beneath this bone and if the pressure continues, the deposition takes the shape of spur, causing pain. Calcaneal spur condition of painful heel can be understood under the term *Vatakantaka*. In Ayurvedic literature. Acharya Sushruta has advised Agnikarma as a treatment modality for the management of *Vatakantaka*. So, Agni karma is selected as choice of treatment in patient with *vatakantaka* i.e. calcaneum spur.

KEYWORDS: Agnikarma, Calcaneum spur, Mruttika shalaka, *Vatakantaka*.

INTRODUCTION

Heel Pain is very common problem in Our Society. Among all diseases of calcaneum the most troublesome common problem seen is calcaneum spur. Pain is cardinal symptoms in most of *vatavyadis*. The word *Vatakantaka* is composed of two words *vata* and *kantaka*. The word *vata* mainly denotes that which has movements which is main causes of action and its derangement causes pain. On the other hand, the word *Kantaka* means thorn which produces sharp stinging pain at heel of foot.

So *vatakantaka* refers to condition caused by *vata* characterized by a sharp stinging pain at heel of foot so Can be correlated with Calcaneum spur.

Major symptoms consist of pain in the region surrounding the spur which typically increases in intensity after prolonged period of rest. Patients may report heel pain to be severe when waking up in morning, the Running, walking or lifting weight may exacerbate the issue. More recent studies have reported that between 11% to 15% of general population has radiographic evidence of calcaneal spur.

Modern treatment of heel pain includes use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) & opioid to reduce pain & inflammation, surgical Excision of Calcaneal spur. Other conservative treatment includes Steroid injection, physiotherapy, cold therapy & heat therapy to relieve pain, inflammation & improve blood circulation to affected area.

Agnikarma, has been described as the most effective therapy in the management of painful conditions especially for musculo-skeletal disorder, such as osteoarthritis, Cervical spondylosis, lumbar spondylosis, plantar fasciitis, Carpal tunnel syndrome, trigger thumb etc. According to Acharya Sushruta Agni is better than kshar in action (of burning), it is so because disease treated by burning will not recur again & those diseases which are incurable by the use of medicine sharp instrument of alkalis will be cured by fire (thermal cautery).

So, Agni karma is selected as choice of treatment in patient with *vatakantaka* i.e. calcaneum spur & treated successfully. So, it is presented in this case study.

CASE REPORT

Patient name XYZ

A 34 years male patient came to OPD with complaints of severe pain and localized tenderness to right heel... 4 months

Difficulty in walking, pain may worsen in posterior aspect of \textcircled{R} heel during working and

Severe pain in morning.

Age -34yrs Sex -female

Date 22/2/2025

History- No k/c/o HTN, DM etc or major illness in past

Afeb

P=76/min

BP = 120/90mm Hg

S/E CVS CNS RS NAD

L/E- tenderness over heel

Investigation

All Investigations normal range.

X-ray shows Right calcaneum spur.

Assessment Criteria

1) Pain at Right Heel (Pain analogue Scale)

Nature Of Pain	Pain Rating
No Pain	0
Mild	1-3
Moderate	4-6
Severe	7-10

2) Distance Walked by patient within.

Distance in feet	Grading
90	0
60	1
30	2
Less than 30	3

Treatment

Agnikarma in form of bindu (point) with *mruṭṭika* (soil) *shalaka* has done.

MATERIALS

Mruṭṭika Shalaka

Candle

Goghṛuta

Madhu

METHODS

Follow up = 4 Follow up after 7 days

Following instructions were given to patients

Give proper rest.

Use proper fitted footwear.

Avoid bare foot walk & standing for long time.

Post *Agnikarma*

Patient advised to apply *Goghṛuta* & *Madhu* over *agnikarma* wound.

Same procedure was adopted at 7 days interval for 4 times.

Follow up on 7th day-Tenderness over affected area & Pain during walking reduced.

Follow up on 28st day-No pain during walking, standing with no tenderness on affected area long time.

OBSERVATIONS

Examinations	Before Treatment	After Treatment
Pain At Heel	10	0
Distance In Feet	3	0

DISCUSSION

In this study *Agnikarma* therapy has done with help of *mruṭṭika shalaka*. Calcaneum spur is correlated with *Vatakantaka vyodhi* & Aacharya Sushruta indicated *agnikarma* in this disease. Cardinal symptoms of Calcaneum spur is pain at heel region. According to ayurveda, basic humour responsible for pain is *vata*. *Vata* dosha having *shit guna* which is opposite to *ushna guna* of *agni* So *agni* is capable of producing relief of pain by its *ushna guna*.

Agni possesses *Ushna*, *Tikshna*, *Sukshma* & *Ashukari* Gunas. Hence it removes *Srota avrodha* & maintains equilibrium of *Agni* also increases *Dhatwagni*, so proper metabolism happens & *Dhatu* gets proper nutrition from *Purva Dhatu*. Also, *Amadosha* from affected site is reduced and *Asthi*, *majja Dhatu* become stable.

Local blood circulation increases due to heat and pain producing substances get washed away and patient gets relief.

CONCLUSION

From this study it is conducted that *Agnikarma* is very effective treatment method of calcaneum spur. It is very simple, less time consuming and very cost-effective method. No hospitalization is needed. New light on quick pain management by ayurvedic treatment is shown. *Agnikarma* is such wonderful part of ayurveda which needs to be explored more. More vast and detailed study with more sample size is needed to scientifically establish the role of *agnikarma* in management of *Vatakantaka* (calcaneum spur).

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